

The WTO's Transformative Role in Promoting Sustainable Development by Integrating Environmental Protection into International Trade

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Introduction

Established in 1994 under the Marrakesh Agreement, the World Trade Organization (WTO) was primarily aimed at promoting global trade and open markets, rather than addressing environmental protection issues. However, the Preamble to the Marrakesh Agreement acknowledges the importance of sustainable development and environmental protection as core objectives for trade liberalization. This formal statement has been acknowledged in WTO case law but has not yet been directly incorporated into a "hard" law within the WTO legal framework.

Environmental protection rules within the WTO legal framework are outlined in Article XX of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT 1994), the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS Agreement), and the Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreement. Generally, these provisions recognize WTO members' right to implement interim environmental policies to achieve legitimate goals, such as protecting the environment, human health, and safety.

Therefore, the WTO Agreement's current role is to find a balance between free trade and environmental protection without making a "hard" law international obligation in the field of environmental protection for members.

One of the most challenging questions in this field concerns how the principle of sustainable development and contemporary environmental protection measures can be integrated into the WTO legal framework. Therefore, this essay aims to explore these issues to analyze the role of the WTO Agreements in environmental protection.

1. The Concept of Sustainable Development and Its Acknowledgment in the WTO Legal Framework

Sustainable development is recognized as an evolving set of legal principles and tools aimed at addressing the imbalance among social, economic, and environmental progress. It has become a guiding principle for laws and legal systems both at the national and international levels¹.

Generally, the concept of sustainable development emerged from the integration of three key elements: economic, social, and environmental. The UN turned the goals of sustainable development into a global call to action to reduce poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030, all people live in peace and prosperity. Recently, this idea has gained widespread

¹ Marie-Claire Cordonier Segger, "Significant Developments in Sustainable Development Law and Governance: A Proposal," *Natural Resources Forum* 28 (2004): 61–74.

recognition and has become the main guiding principle for government planning and domestic policy development. The WTO has officially adopted sustainable development as a goal, stating that trade should be managed to optimize the use of the world's resources in line with this aim. In other words, achieving sustainable development is a formal goal of the WTO².

At the same time, sustainable development operates at the intersection of two conflicting priorities in WTO law: the right to free trade and economic growth, and the right to restrict trade to protect life, health, and the environment³.

However, beyond the Preamble, the WTO and its agreements have largely neglected to make sustainable development a binding obligation for member states. Developing countries view sustainable development in the WTO with suspicion. Its focus on intergenerational equity, prioritizing growth between current and future generations, may overshadow the need to urgently address income inequality between the rich and the poor worldwide. Additionally, if sustainable development means emphasizing environmental or labor standards, it could introduce a new form of conditionality in global trade. Developing countries strongly oppose their inclusion in the WTO on these grounds⁴.

The WTO legal framework's sustainable development objectives, such as a "WTO sustainability agenda," are being discussed in ongoing negotiations, particularly with respect to climate change mitigation. The WTO's general exceptions safeguard human rights values related to sustainable development, including public health protection, the conservation of exhaustible natural resources, and environmental protection⁵.

This indicates that the WTO's legal framework for sustainable development objectives remains evolving. In other words, the WTO seeks to balance the right to free trade and economic growth with environmental protection, but it does not aim to be the primary actor in establishing ecological norms or setting standards for member states. While the concept of sustainable development is a declaration of priorities for global growth, it can influence free trade and create new trade barriers for developing countries that pay less attention to environmental issues and face environmental measures when accessing global markets.

2. Contemporary Environmental Measures in Global Trade and the WTO

Some authors identify contemporary trade-related environmental protection policy measures as lowering tariffs on environmental goods and subsidizing trade in renewable energy, both of which are relevant to climate change abatement.

Trade agreements can help achieve climate goals by removing tariffs, harmonizing environmental standards, and eliminating fossil-fuel subsidies. However, the effectiveness of these agreements is often hindered by large corporations. For instance, trade agreements on emission reduction are weak due to protectionism and conflicting national interests.

² D. Robertson, review of *The WTO and Sustainable Development*, by Gary P. Sampson (Tokyo: United Nations University Press, 2005): 8.

³ Gabrielle Marceau and Fabio C. Morosini, "The Status of Sustainable Development in the Law of the World Trade Organization" (paper, November 8, 2011): 71–72.

⁴ Robertson, *supra* note 2, at 8.

⁵ Ernst Ulrich Petersmann, "The World Trading System, Human Rights and Sustainable Development," in *Business, Human Rights and Sustainable Development* (2025): 169.

As previously noted under WTO agreements, countries are granted significant autonomy to set their own environmental protection goals and to adopt and implement environmental legislation, provided they comply with WTO principles⁶. Additionally, many bilateral, regional, and interregional free trade agreements include detailed environmental provisions that create incentives for producers to adopt sustainable practices to gain and maintain access to new markets⁷.

Environmental measures in global trade have given rise to "green regionalism," a new normative process within regional economic frameworks that integrates environmental sustainability into international trade law. Recent developments in U.S. and EU trade agreements, along with new Asia-Pacific green economy pacts, exemplify green regionalism.

For instance, the European Union's proposed Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) is a modern trade policy designed to impose a carbon price on imported goods, aiming to address weaknesses in the EU's current cap-and-trade system and to encourage global emissions reductions.

However, the analysis of the potential conflict between CBAM and the WTO rules suggests that a dispute could arise when examining similar trade measures protected under Article XX of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). Given the WTO's focus on sustainable development, a waiver from global trade rules should be granted for measures such as the CBAM, which are specifically designed to reduce carbon emissions⁸.

Other recently proposed contemporary environmental measures in international trade include the US Border Carbon Adjustment (BCA) and the Global Steel and Aluminium Arrangement (GSAA). However, the focus of these measures varies across agreements. CBAM focuses narrowly on price-based policies and explicit carbon prices, whereas the BCA and GSAA adopt a broader approach centered on environmental equivalence and punitive measures⁹.

An alternative approach to temporary environmental measures in international trade involves special subsidy agreements for environmentally important sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, and fossil fuels. Rules in the Tokyo Round Subsidies Code and the WTO SCM Agreement concerning subsidies, particularly those deemed environmentally harmful, have limited influence on environmental protection but exert a significant impact on international trade¹⁰.

3. The WTO Case Law Relating to the Protection of the Environment

The WTO's dispute settlement system plays a critical role in shaping and broadening the organization's environmental case law¹¹. The evolution of WTO jurisdiction on cases involving

⁶ Robert Howse, "The World Trade Organization 20 Years On: Global Governance by Judiciary," *European Journal of International Law* 27, no. 1 (2016): 9–77.

⁷ Christophe Bellmann and C. van der Ven, *Greening Regional Trade Agreements on Non-Tariff Measures through Technical Barriers to Trade and Regulatory Co-operation*, OECD Trade and Environment Working Papers no. 2020/04 (Paris: OECD, 2020).

⁸ Delaney Smith, "The Legality of the European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism and the Limitations of World Trade Organization Rules on Effective Climate Action" (2022).

⁹ Giulia Claudia Leonelli, "Carbon Border Measures, Environmental Effectiveness and WTO Law Compatibility: Is There a Way Forward for the Steel and Aluminium Climate Club?" *World Trade Review* 21, no. 5 (2022): 619–632.

¹⁰ Ronald Steenblik, "Addressing Environmentally Harmful Subsidies Using Trade Rules: A Historical Perspective," in *The Elgar Companion to the World Trade Organization* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2023): 551–573.

¹¹ Fariborz Zelli, "The World Trade Organization: Free Trade and Its Environmental Impacts," in *Handbook of Globalization and the Environment* (London: Routledge, 2017): 177–216.

environmental trade measures, such as the use of Article XX of GATT as a rationale for imposing trade restrictions, has assumed greater importance in balancing competing perspectives.

Specific WTO rulings illustrate the need for caution when interpreting environmental measures as less restrictive and the requirement of non-discrimination in their application¹². These WTO environmental cases are considered important milestones in the use of environmental considerations to justify trade-restrictive measures.

In the 1997 "Shrimp-Turtle" dispute, India, Malaysia, Pakistan, and Thailand filed a joint complaint with the WTO against the United States' ban on imports of shrimp and shrimp products. The Appellate Body of the WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism noted that, under WTO rules, countries have the right to take measures to protect the environment, in particular to protect endangered species and depleted resources, and that measures to protect sea turtles would be lawful under Article XX of the GATT (which deals with exceptions to WTO trade rules, including for certain environmental reasons) provided that certain criteria are met, such as non-discrimination¹³. A similar decision was made in a 2007 case concerning a ban on the import of retreaded tires from the European Union into Brazil. The Appellate Body concluded that Brazil's ban on imports of retreaded tires and the penalties it imposed were inconsistent¹⁴.

In the 1995 "US - Standards for Reformulated and Conventional Gasoline case", both the Panel and the Appellate Body found that the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) "Gasoline Rule" violated Article III:4 of the GATT because it treated imported gasoline "less favorably" than "like" domestic gasoline. However, the Appellate Body found a violation of Article III of the GATT by the US - Gasoline Regulation as being excused as an environmental protection measure under Article XX (g) of the GATT. The Appellate Body defined "exhaustible natural resource" in the meaning of Art. XX (g) of the GATT in that manner, that it can be applied to living and non-living resources, and added that this term should be interpreted broadly in accordance with current environmental protection conventions.

The Panel's decision on the "US - Standards for Reformulated and Conventional Gasoline case" was the first time in the history of the WTO that an environmental protection measure was considered justified under Article XX (b) of the GATT.

In the landmark case *European Communities – Measures Concerning Meat and Meat Products (Hormones)*, the WTO Appellate Body addressed the relationship between trade measures and the protection of human health within the framework of the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS Agreement). The Appellate Body acknowledged the right of WTO Members to establish their own "appropriate level of sanitary or phytosanitary protection", a sovereign prerogative, but it is not unlimited. Article 3.3 of the SPS Agreement permits members to maintain measures that provide a higher level of protection than that provided by international standards, but such measures must be supported by a risk assessment and sufficient scientific evidence¹⁵.

¹² Robert Falkner and Nico Jaspers, "Environmental Protection, International Trade and the WTO," in *The Ashgate Research Companion to International Trade Policy* (2016): 245–260.

¹³ Appellate Body Report, *United States – Import Prohibition of Certain Shrimp and Shrimp Products*, WT/DS58/AB/R (October 12, 1998).

¹⁴ Panel and Appellate Body Reports, *Brazil – Measures Affecting Imports of Retreaded Tyres*, WT/DS332 (summary of key findings).

¹⁵ Panel Report, *European Communities – Measures Concerning Meat and Meat Products (Hormones)*, WT/DS26/R/USA (August 18, 1997).

Decisions by the WTO Dispute Settlement Bodies in international disputes, including an examination of the application of GATT Article XX to environmental protection measures, demonstrate that the WTO has found such measures consistent with Article XX in most cases concerning environmental protection¹⁶, which still should be used without discrimination and supported by a risk assessment and sufficient scientific evidence.

4. The Future Role of WTO Agreements in Environmental Protection and Sustainable Development

Strengthening and reforming the WTO require a clear understanding of the relationship between trade rules and the Sustainable Development Goals, including an evaluation of options to modify or create trade policy agreements¹⁷.

Some authors suggest future actions for the WTO, such as adopting a proactive approach to the impact of inefficient fossil-fuel subsidies on climate change and enhancing disclosure rules for member states to promote transparency and accountability¹⁸. Such a trade agreement, by integrating trade into the 2030 Agenda and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals, can make the WTO a central organization for achieving these global targets.

The WTO could become a "next-generation organization" by creating mechanisms to support trade-related agreements that address social policies, such as labor regulations and environmental protection¹⁹. These policies are vital for establishing fair trade rules in accordance with the sustainable development concept.

Conclusion

WTO agreements do not directly regulate environmental issues, but they establish legal principles for such regulation through WTO case law that recognizes interim measures adopted by member states for environmental protection. A clear example is Article XX(b) of the GATT, which allows measures "necessary to protect human, animal, or plant life or health." At the same time, the WTO can play a transformative role in promoting sustainable development globally by establishing special trading measures in its international agreements. While provisions in current WTO trade agreements indicate that environmental protection primarily serves as a means for countries to lawfully implement interim policies without limiting free trade or discriminating against imports, a set of rules governing these interim policies is necessary. WTO case law can also support this idea.

At the same time, the future of the WTO could be very promising in regulating environmental protection measures, but it depends on the actions of key stakeholders and the international trade law agenda. The future of international law remains uncertain, as its rules can still be used to favor major countries rather than promote global trade and economic development, especially in the context of sustainable development.

¹⁶ Y. Shafiee and Caroline Rosie Jeffrey Nasah, "The Effect of Article XX of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) on Environmental Protection Measures: The Case of Malaysia," *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences* 13 (2023): 12.

¹⁷ Gary P. Sampson, "The WTO, Trade Agreements, and Sustainable Trade," *Asia Policy* 16, no. 4 (2021): 7–21.

¹⁸ Anamika Shukla, "The Future of Trade and Environment: A Roadmap for Reconciling Two Competing Goals," *Journal of World Trade* 58, no. 1 (2024).

¹⁹ Kathleen Claussen, "Next-Generation Agreements and the WTO," *World Trade Review* 21, no. 3 (2022): 380–388.